

GENDER AND COGNITIVE PERFORMANCE: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The cognitive performance of human resources plays a crucial role in any work related to organizational development. The existing literature sheds light on many factors that can influence cognitive aspects of human performance. However, the role of gender remains unexplored, which makes the present study different from existing knowledge. In this study, I have examined the influence of gender on three aspects of cognitive performance: forgetfulness, distractibility, and false triggering. The study was conducted on a sample of 80 employees with more than a decade of experience at Indian universities. Data was collected through the Cognitive Failures Questionnaire (Broadbent, 1982), and analysis was carried out by applying appropriate statistical techniques with the help of IBM SPSS (version 25). The results indicated that the cognitive performance of employees does not depend on gender. Therefore, the study is relevant for business leaders and executives, especially in the context of recruitment, placement, training, maintenance, and retention of employees, thus enhancing organizational effectiveness. Following a discussion, I have provided directions for future research.

Key words: Gender, Organization, Business, Cognitive Performance

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1. INTRODUCTION

Human beings are born to perform any specific task in their lives depending upon their socio-economic status, cultural upbringing, and educational qualifications. However, in the real world, we find that some people are good performers and some are poor performers, even though their socioeconomic status, cultural upbringing, and educational qualifications are the same.

Similar is the case with two contrasting employees, i.e., Manoj and Archana (names are not denoting anyone in person), who started their careers at the same time, but after ten years down the line, their achievements are significantly different. Manoj has been a good performer in his previous examinations, such as high school and intermediate. Later on, he completed his graduation in engineering from a reputed Indian university, but in this course, he could not perform well. Then he started his professional life with a small organization and subsequently struggled a lot to establish himself in all possible ways. On the contrary, Archana, who has been a poor performer during her high school and intermediate examinations and therefore could not complete even graduation, started her own play school with the support of her spouse and established herself professionally, consequently earning well. There may be many similar cases that we observe or read about, and we try to understand the causes of such cases. Researchers have established various reasons for this phenomenon (Abubakar and Wang, 2019) in this context, but among those reasons, cognitive reasons may be the most prominent (Broadbent et al., 1982). For instance, some people are good at mathematics or problem solving but not at memorizing biological or historical concepts, due to which there is a variation in their marks during high school or intermediate examinations. However, these marks do not guarantee that these people will not achieve anything in their professional lives. Therefore, cognitive performance plays an important role in one's life and thereby needs to be studied from multiple angles. With this backdrop, the present study is an attempt to understand the cognitive functioning of human beings and its correlation with its various dimensions.

According to the seminal study by Broadbent (1982), every human being makes mistakes or errors at some point of time in their professional lives. Most of the time, these mistakes or errors do not result from a lack of knowledge or ability; rather, they occur when we are unable to focus on the task at hand or, occasionally, when we are unable to recall (memorize) the events or episodes. In this study, three dimensions of cognitive failure have been identified: forgetfulness, distraction, and false triggering. Forgetfulness refers to the lapse of memory; distraction refers to the lack of attention; and false triggering refers to irrelevant mental activities that are primarily due to mental disorders. This study has a practical application in contemporary professional life when people (employees) forget the names of those they meet or forget their keys to vehicles or even houses. Sometimes these people (employees) are also unable to focus on important things and easily distracted by external stimuli, and finally, due to some psychiatric problems, they are also engaged in irrelevant mental activities that are meaningless from others points of view. On the basis of this seminal study, Džubur et al. (2020) examined the causes and consequences of cognitive failure in a sample of 175 first-year students at the University of Sarajevo. The researchers argue that it is stress and anxiety that trigger cognitive failures among students, and as a consequence, these students use cigarettes, alcohol, and other similar products for relaxation. This scenario is also visible even in premier Indian institutions such as IITs and IIMs and therefore needs significant attention from the researchers' point of view. Džubur et al. (2020) have also found that anxiety is statistically significantly correlated with the total number of cognitive failures and its other dimensions such as forgetfulness, distractibility, and false triggering. Moreover, with the increasing participation of women employees in almost all employment sectors (Grant Thornton, 2022), gender has become an important issue for researchers. However, there is a dearth of studies that can examine cognitive performance across genders, and thereby this study is unique in this sense.

Age has been another variable that is commonly associated with the organizational performance of employees (Guzzo et al., 2022; Žepič, 2021) and thereby it has been considered in the present study. Despite the rising interest in cognitive understandings of organizational variables (Akiomi et al., 2021; Abbasi et al., 2017), I do not find any substantive studies in organizational context. Hence, this is the first study in this direction that examines the cognitive performance of employees (faculty members working in academia) from a dimensional point of view. The present study is also significant in including the increasing role of cognitive performance through psychological capital in achieving business excellence in many organizations (Sheng-Hsun Hsu et al., 2014).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

In the contemporary globalized business world, organizations have to perform well in order to survive and expand their business domains. This business performance largely depends on the efforts of human resources (employees) in the organization, who can perform in cognitive or non-cognitive ways. When these employees perform in a cognitive way, they achieve the results, and if they fail cognitively, they struggle to achieve the target. Therefore, cognitive performance has become a necessary condition for the success of human beings. According to Harvey (2019), ‘cognitive performance is typically conceptualized in terms of all domains of a business. These domains are hierarchical in nature, with the bottom referring to more basic sensory and perceptual processes and the top referring to elements of executive functioning and cognitive control’. Van Orden et al. (2003) have conducted an experimental study related to human performance and background noise. He has concluded that it is self-organizing behavior that governs the cognitive performance of human beings. Although I could not find much detail about this experimental study, in general it is quite pertinent to the existing literature and therefore needs attention by organizational researchers.

There may be various tasks in an organization that can be classified as cognitive or non-cognitive, and thereby, people (employees) cannot be deployed randomly to any task. This is not so common in a well-structured organization, especially in academic organizations (institutions or universities of higher education), but I have experienced that in most academic organizations it happens. As a consequence, employees find no meaning in their jobs (Fornaciari and Dean, 2005), and if it persists for a long time, it damages the cognitive functioning of the employees. In this process, most of the main employees become habitual performers in a non-cognitive way and eventually do not contribute to the development of the organization in a real sense. However, social role theory (Steed et al., 2023) believes that there is differentiation in the functional roles of employees based on gender (Raja, 2020). Therefore, many organizations prefer female employees for some specific positions and roles, but when it comes to cognitive tasks, they face problems in decision-making. This phenomenon has motivated the author of the present article to examine the role of gender in cognitive performance, or, in other words, to compare cognitive performance across genders. Although Harvey (2019) conceptualized cognitive performance in terms of domains of functioning, I contend that this is not a direct measurement of the three dimensions of cognitive performance, i.e., forgetfulness, distractibility, and false triggering, proposed by Boradbent et al. (1982). Keeping these views in mind, the literature has been confined to associating gender with the aforementioned three dimensions.

2.1. Gender and Forgetfulness

Loprinzi and Frith (2018) have given evidence related to the contribution of biological sex to the memory function of human beings. They argue that there may be several mechanisms, such as neuroanatomy, through which people remember things. However, this study is unable to clearly establish whether men or women have better memory function. Similarly, Manthorpe and Samsi (2020) have examined the role of gender in dementia (which is an indication of weak intellectual functioning, especially related to memory). Additionally, a study conducted by Holman et al. (2013) also examined the role of gender in memory functioning and found that men have more memory problems as compared to women. Although this study has given some hints for making directional hypotheses, there is much to explore. Alzheimer's is another disease that is related to the memory function of human beings. In this context, Andrew and Tierney (2018) have conducted a narrative review and found that there is a difference in cognitive performance across gender, and the reasons could be biological ones or societal ones wherein some tasks are categorized on the basis of gender. But it lacks in terms of directional hypotheses, and therefore a research gap exists here. In an experimental study, Niedźwieńska¹ and Zielińska (2021), they tested the relationship of marital status with the memory function of men and women. They have suggested organizing premarital workshops and dealing with these issues from a psychological perspective. Still, they could not answer the basic question: who has better memory, men or women? Therefore, again, there is a lacuna in the available literature. In light of the aforementioned studies, if we observe the contemporary professional lives of women employees, we find they have mostly multiple responsibilities, sometimes as a spouse, sometimes as a mother or sister, and sometimes as a grandmother. Under these circumstances, it is really worthwhile to appreciate the women employees having more memory space, without which they cannot perform professionally or personally. With this backdrop, I propose the first hypothesis:

H1: Women employees have better memory as compared to men employees, and therefore they do not forget things easily. Hence, forgetfulness (dimension of cognitive performance) is less among women employees as compared to men employees

2.2. Gender and Distractibility

As far as distraction is concerned, Ambron and Foroni (2016) have tried to understand the basic causes of distractibility from a gender perspective, but the findings are not very clear, and hence, there is a further requirement for studies in this context. A similar study has been conducted by Strahler et al. (2019), wherein it has been found that men and women are different in terms of their focus, and thereby their attentive behavior is also different. Moreover, this study also confirms that men employees pay deep attention to any stimulus as compared to women employees, which appears true in the organizational context. However, in recent times, it has been observed in India that women students are getting better positions in board of corporates and civil service examinations (The Hindu Bureau, 2023), which clearly indicates that women are better at attentive behavior as compared to men. As there is contradiction on these issues, 'generalization cannot be done; I am proposing the second hypothesis with reference to the Indian culture as follows:

H2: Women employees are better in their attentive behaviors and thereby, they experience less distraction as compared to men employees

2.3. Gender and False Triggering

The third dimension of cognitive performance is related to irrelevant mental activities, which are generally called "false triggering". Though I could not find any relevant study in this context, on the basis of the gender and managerial perspectives (Tabassum and Nayak, 2021; Moè, 2009), I assume that women employees are equally competent in cognitive performance, which may be due to their disengagement in irrelevant mental activities, and therefore the third hypothesis is:

H3: False triggering is less among women employees as compared to men employees

3. METHODOLOGY

Any job or task can be generally categorized into two types: the first is cognitive, and the second is non-cognitive (Indeed Editorial Team, 2022). Non-cognitive tasks are related to soft skills, which is not a point of concern in the present article. Cognitive tasks are those that require critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and other complex mental operations. According to Kester and Kirschner (2012), 'cognitive tasks are those undertakings that require a person to mentally process new information and allow them to recall, retrieve, and use that information at a later time in the same or similar situation'. Teaching (especially at the university level) is an area that needs this kind of mental processing. Therefore, we have selected the education sector as a sampling frame, out of which initially 140 faculty members (respondents) with more than a decade of experience were selected randomly. These faculty members are working at different reputed private universities in India, and they are from different states of India (i.e., a different representation of the population). The randomly selected faculty members were informed about the purpose of the survey, and eventually they were given the standard questionnaire (Broadbent et al., 1982), which has three dimensions (forgetfulness, distractibility, and false triggering). As there is no direct measure of cognitive performance, we have prepared the composite score of cognitive performance by adding the scores of the three dimensions. The employees (faculty members) were requested to complete the questionnaire within the shortest possible time. Out of 140, I received only eighty (80) questionnaires, which were filled out without any missing data (the response rate is 57%). Though the sample size is small, it qualifies the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test for further analysis. The average age of the employees is approximately 43 (42.84 years), which also indicates the current Indian demographic dividend. Out of eighty employees, 45 are men, and the remaining 35 are women. Data has been analyzed by applying suitable statistical tests (Krishnaswamy et al., 2018) with the help of IBM software, i.e., SPSS (v. 25). The reliability (Cronbach's alpha) of the scales is: cognitive performance (.876), forgetfulness (.695), distractibility (.758), and false trigger (.622), which further indicates the acceptability of all the developed scales not only at the international level but also in the Indian context.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.623
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	366.701
	df	6
	Sig.	.000

Table 1 indicates that the selected sample size is not enough to capture the various dimensions of cognitive performance. However, a value of 0.632 is not so poor as to ignore the sample size. Hence, we move on to further analysis.

Figure.1

According to the Cognitive Failure Questionnaire (Broadbent, 1982), there are three dimensions of overall cognitive performance (forgetfulness, distractibility, and false triggers) that are shown in Figure 1.

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics						
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic
Cognitive Performance	80	4.00	53.00	33.2625	12.91035	-.611
Forgetfulness	80	2.00	21.00	12.4250	4.83598	-.208
Distractibility	80	1.00	17.00	10.5375	4.75726	-.305
False Triggering	80	2.00	19.00	9.0000	4.15522	.183
Valid N (listwise)	80					

Skewness refers to the extent to which values deviate from symmetry around the mean. In Table 2, skewness is close to zero in all cases (cognitive performance and its three dimensions), which shows that the psychometric characteristics of the data are reasonably good.

Table 3

Descriptive Statistics			
	Skewness	Kurtosis	
	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Cognitive Performance	.269	-.116	.532
Forgetfulness	.269	-.185	.532
Distractibility	.269	-.521	.532
False Triggering	.269	.637	.532
Valid N (listwise)			

Similarly, the values of kurtosis as shown in Table 3 are close to zero or the minimum, which indicates that the data is normally distributed to a large extent.

Table 4

Group Statistics					
	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Cognitive Performance	Women	35	31.9143	15.63625	2.64301
	Men	45	34.3111	10.38098	1.54750
Forgetfulness	Women	35	12.2286	5.61031	.94832
	Men	45	12.5778	4.19680	.62562
Distractibility	Women	35	9.5429	4.68001	.79107
	Men	45	11.3111	4.72336	.70412
False Triggering	Women	35	10.4286	4.99580	.84444
	Men	45	7.8889	2.97124	.44293

Now, I come to the results, which are related to the proposed hypotheses. The independent sample t-test (Table 4) shows that for the overall score of cognitive performance, 35 women have a mean of 31.91 and 45 men have a mean of 334.31, which appears to be different, which means that men have better cognitive performance as compared to women. This may be a reason why women have less participation in jobs that require more cognition as compared to men. For instance, in India, we generally observe that parents motivate their girl child to go for graduation in arts or humanities-related subjects as compared to engineering or medicine (though the trend is changing because of the "*Beti Bachao Beti Padhao*" Scheme sponsored by the Government of India). In the case of forgetfulness (a dimension of cognitive performance), the mean of women (12.23) and men (12.58) is almost the same, which indicates that as far as memory function is concerned, both men and women are equal. At this point, it is important to bring up the Norwegian study by Holmen et al. (2013), which found that there is a difference in memory function when it comes to gender. However, my findings do not support the reported result, which may be because Norway and India have different cultures. Similarly, Niedźwieńska and Zielińska (2021) have examined cognition in terms of memory on the basis of marital status and reported the difference. Additionally, although Laws et al.'s (2016) study does not directly support our findings, it suggests that men and women have different cognitive abilities.

Nonetheless, the second dimension of cognitive performance is distractibility, where men and women differ in their mean score (Table 5). In this context, Kanai et al. (2011) contend that brain structure is the primary determinant of distractibility, a common phenomenon in our daily lives. As brain structure is different between men and women (Luders and Kurth, 2020), there is a difference in attentive behavior, which overtly refers to distractibility. Finally, the third dimension of cognitive performance is false triggering, which refers to irrelevant mental activity. In this dimension, men and women differ (Table 5). In other words, it indicates that men are involved in many activities that are not always relevant, but on the other hand, women engage themselves only in meaningful activities. This may be the reason for the growing participation of women in corporate boardrooms. Although these differences in mean exist, they cannot be statistically significant, for which we have to look at the next table (Table 5).

Table 5

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances					
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig (2 tailed)
Cognitive Performance	Equal variances assumed	4.46	.04	-0.82	78	.41
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.78	56.20	.44
Forgetfulness	Equal variances assumed	2.31	.13	-0.32	78	.75
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.31	61.09	.76
Distractibility	Equal variances assumed	.471	.50	-1.67	78	.01
	Equal variances not assumed			2.83	73.54	.01
False Triggering	Equal variances assumed	3.35	.07	2.66	78	.01
	Equal variances not assumed				52.23	.01

Kindly look at the values shown in Table 5, which are highlighted in bold. These values indicate that, though it appears that men and women differ in their cognitive performance (forgetfulness, distractibility, and false triggering), these differences are statistically not significant. Therefore, all the hypotheses (H1, H2, and H3) are rejected. There may be many reasons for such insignificant results, among which contemporary changes in the mindset of employers are the most prominent. That is the reason that now we find men and women are equally good performers in terms of cognition and thereby cannot be differentiated in jobs of any type (engineering, medical, banking, etc.).

5. CONCLUSION

The present research paper has compared overall cognitive performance and its three dimensions (forgetfulness, distractibility, and false triggering) across genders and divulged the fact that men and women are equally competent in terms of cognition. This implies that Indian society is changing its thoughts about gender and its role in various occupations. This may be the strongest reason that more and more women and men are coming into the academic field, and through higher education, they are contributing to teaching and research kinds of jobs, which are cognitive in nature. Still, we have a long way to go before the human resources of academic organizations, especially private universities in India, can develop their cognitive skills through training without any differentiation based on gender. Though I have conducted the present study in a small sample of employees (faculty members), I believe that this study will contribute to the existing literature on cognitive performance and that its findings can be useful for academic leaders during recruitment, training, and promotional aspects of human resource development. Future researchers are encouraged to replicate this study in a large and diversified sample of various other sectors that are different from academia. They may also consider the cultural aspects of different countries for similar studies at the global level.

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Gender and Cognitive Performance: A Comparative Study

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